

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D2.1 KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND MUTUAL LEARNING PLAN 30/06/2023

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

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Grant Agreement No.: 101094917
Topic: HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-51
Type of action: CSA

D2.1 KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND MUTUAL LEARNING PLAN

Document information

Work package	WP 2
Task	Task 2.2 Development of the knowledge sharing methodology
Due date	30/06/2023
Submission date	30/06/2023
Deliverable lead	APRE
Version	1.0
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Authors	Laura Mentini (APRE)
Editors	Maria Carmela Fierro (APRE)
Reviewers	Chiara Pocaterra (APRE)
Abstract	This document represents the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning Plan which defines the approach, contents and activities of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning process which will be developed throughout the CATALISI project, with the overall aim of strengthening R&I in the European Research Area.
Keywords	Knowledge sharing; Mutual learning; Higher Education Institutions; Twinning; Institutional transformation; Methodology

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	24/05/2023	Structure of the content	Laura Mentini (APRE)
0.2	08/06/2023	First Version	Laura Mentini (APRE) Chiara Pocaterra (APRE)
0.3	14/06/2023	First Version Shared amongst partners	Laura Mentini (APRE)
0.4	23/06/2023	Comments and feedbacks provided	Partners
0.5	28/06/2023	Integration and editing	Laura Mentini (APRE)
1.0	30/06/2023	Version submitted	Laura Mentini (APRE)

CATALISI consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA	APRE	ITALY
2	ERNST & YOUNG ADVISORY SPA	EY	ITALY
3	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	F6S	IRELAND
4	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	BELGIUM
5	KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS	KTU	LITHUANIA
6	UNIVERSITAT JAUME I DE CASTELLON	UJI	SPAIN
7	LUISS LIBERA UNIVERSITA INTERNAZIONALE DEGLI STUDI SOCIALI GUIDO CARLI	LUISS	ITALY
8	UNIWERSYTET GDANSKI	UG	POLAND
9	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK	UCC	IRELAND
10	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	GREECE
11	STICHTING VUMC	VUMC	NETHERLANDS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this document is to provide a guide for CATALISI partners in the organization of the activities foreseen in the Knowledge sharing programme (WP2) based on the experiences collected during the co-creation of Living labs (WP1) as well as the needs, competences, available methods and tools, and implementers priority interests. The plan describes the framework, guidelines and implementation plan of mutual learning and knowledge exchange designed to support the activities of WP3 that will guarantee the design, the implementation and the sustainability of the institutional transformations.

This document represents the approach, contents and activities of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning process which will be developed throughout the CATALISI project, amongst the implementers, and all partners in general, with the overall aim of strengthening R&I in the European Research Area.

The document includes the Introduction to the project and the deliverable; the state of the art of MML in CATALISI; the aim of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual learning plan; the types of activities foreseen, and the shape and schedule of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning events.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Contents

LIST OF FIGURES	5
LIST OF TABLES	6
1. Introduction	8
1.1. Background and aim	8
1.2. Aim and structure of the deliverable	8
2. State of the art of MML in CATALISI	9
3. Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning approach in CATALISI	11
4. Set up of the Knowledge Sharing and Mutual Learning Events	13
4.1 MML onsite workshops	13
4.2 Mutual Learning online events	15
4.3 Twinning Schemes	17
5. Capitalisation of knowledge and know-how	18
6. Shape of the MML Events	18
6.1 Define the output/outcome	19
6.2 Identify the topic	19
6.3 Identify stakeholders and select participants	20
6.4 Define the activities	21
6.5 Evaluation of MMLs	21
6.6 MML formats and techniques	21
7. Schedule of the knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events	23
7.1 Timeline of MML workshops	23
7.2 Timeline of Twinning Schemes	24
8. CONCLUSION	25
9. References	26
Appendix A – Draft MML EVENT Report	27
Appendix B – Draft TWINNING Report	29

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1 Results from survey - Are you familiar with the Mobilization and Mutual Learning (MML) methodology and workshops?</i>	<i>10</i>
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Figure 2 results from survey - Do you use MML methodology to facilitate transformations and produce research & innovation in your HEI?.....10

Figure 3 results from survey - opportunities of MML in catalisi 12

Figure 4: Preliminary overview of topics considered relevant for MML onsite workshops by CATALISI HEIs..... 15

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 - Structure of Onsite MML workshops..... 14

Table 3 Twinning methodology in CATALISI..... 18

Table 4: List of techniques for MML workshops..... 22

Table 5 Tentative Timeline for onsite MML workshops..... 24

Table 6 Tentative Timeline for MML online events..... 24

Table 7 Tentative Timeline for Twinning Schemes..... 25

ABBREVIATIONS

D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
HEI	Higher Education Institution
M	Month
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
R&I	Research and Innovation
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
GA	Grant Agreement
CoP	Community of Practice

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND AIM

Institutional transformation is a key strategy to address the challenges of Research and Innovation (R&I) and to govern and drive the transformations affecting science and innovation. Institutional changes of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) enables to better align R&I and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society (European Commission, 2020). Research and Innovation topics have been in fact geared towards establishing institutional changes in education institutes opening them up to closer cooperation with citizens and civil society.

With these premises in mind, the CATALISI project is overall aimed at contributing to the EC objective of spreading and embedding Research & Innovation in the European Research Area through the facilitation and acceleration of institutional transformations of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in seven research organisations. The overall objective of the project is to assist HEIs to successfully implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation benefitting of acceleration services.

For each research organisation, institutional transformations will be incorporated in a strategy and individual pathway that will provide the basis for medium and long terms sustainable institutional change towards R&I. In fact, Institutional transformation is expected to have meaningful impact within the institution concerned and intended to last beyond the lifetime of project funding (European Commission, 2020). In CATALISI, transformational pathways will set the ground and "pave the way" towards long-term changes.

To achieve institutional transformation, HEIs will benefit from seven targeted and innovative acceleration services: Living Labs, Design lab for transformational pathway; Counselling; Reinforce Human Capital; Predictive study on skills anticipation; Marketplace; Community of practice (CoP). Also, HEIs are committed to introduce and implement new reforms in their structures intervening on specific domains and intervention areas. The domains identified in CATALISI are: Human Capital, Research Modus Operandi and Finance, which respectively composed by different intervention areas, that indicate the content of specific institutional transformations that can be deemed necessary by each HEIs.

The project involves 11 partners, of which 7 are the HEIs, who will pursue institutional transformations (so-called "implementers") while 4 (the so-called "facilitators") will assist the HEIs to implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation.

To support this process, a set of specific actions included in WP2, "Knowledge sharing and mutual learning programme", led by APRE, are envisaged for encouraging and supporting mutual learning dynamics and to integrate the endeavours of the HEIs in the development of institutional transformations in the field of R&I.

1.2. AIM AND STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable represents the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning Plan which defines approach, contents and activities of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning process which will be developed throughout the CATALISI project. In particular, this deliverable aims to provide implementing partners with practical guidelines for the design of Mobilisation and Mutual learning (MML) approach and Twinning schemes that are relevant to the design and implementation of institutional change, based on the best practices and lessons learnt, the

needs, competences, available methods and tools and implementers priority interests collected during the needs assessment (WP1).

The document is organised in seven sections, including this **section 1** devoted to the Introduction to the project and to the deliverable.

- **Section 2** illustrates the state of the art of MML in CATALISI.
- **Section 3** highlights the aims of the Knowledge Sharing and Mutual learning in CATALISI
- **Section 4** provides an overview of the type of knowledge sharing and mutual learning events foreseen
- **Section 5** illustrates capitalisation of knowledge and know-how
- **Section 6** describes the shape and methodology for MML activities
- The scheduling of the events is finally illustrated in **Section 7**

- **Appendix A:** presenting the Draft MML Event report
- **Appendix B:** Presenting the Draft Twinning report

2. STATE OF THE ART OF MML IN CATALISI

Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) actions are intended to tackle Research and Innovation related challenges by creating partnerships with a variety of perspectives, knowledge and experience. MML actions are also intended to ensure that Research and Innovation is not only excellent, but also relevant and responsive to the needs of all ¹.

On the one hand, CATALISI builds upon the knowledge of **consortium partners** in the organisation of MML activities and workshops. Specifically, APRE has a consolidated experience, as coordinator of projects which have utilised MML methodology, such as H2020 BIOVOICES (G.A. n. 774331) and H2020 TIMES4SC (G.A. n. 101006201). The outputs, deliverables and lessons learnt from these projects are beneficial for the organisation and set-up of MML in CATALISI. Specifically:

1. "D3.4 *Guide for MML workshops*" of the BIOVOICES project, presents a methodology for partners in the utilisation of MML for the bioeconomy. In this context, the quadruple helix actors involved are related to relevant stakeholders groups to address and tackle bio-based related challenges.
2. "D3.2 *Second version of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning plan*" in TIME4SC H2020 project, is concerned with knowledge sharing and Mutual learning to support HEIs institutional transformation with the ultimate goal to encourage Public Engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology.

Other relevant **EU-funded projects** highlighted by CATALISI project partners, and that have utilised MML methodology are:

- MARINA H2020 project (G.A. ID: 710566). Specifically, the "D3.1 *MML Workshop Methodology Approach and Actor Inclusion Criteria*" highlights the use of MML to engage citizens, researchers, businesses and policy makers in marine Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) – APRE partner.
- Grace H2020 project (G.A. 824521) develops a *Mutual Learning Plan* (D.3.1) for the achievement of RRI-oriented institutional change of HEIs.
- SISCODE H2020 project (G.A. 788217), which aim is to stimulating the use of co-creation methodologies in policy design, to pollinate Responsible Research and Innovation, and Science Technology and Innovation Policies – APRE partner.

¹ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_HCO-15-2014.

On the other hand, an internal **online survey** has been sent by APRE in May 2023 (M5) to each HEI in CATALISI to assess the state of the art of CATALISI Implementing partners on the knowledge regarding MML activities within their respective host organisation. Results from the online survey indicate two main aspects:

1. The majority of respondents (46%) are partially familiar with the MML methodology, 30% are not familiar at all with this methodology, and only 23% are familiar with the MML methodology. Therefore, the level of knowledge amongst team members within each university varies.

FIGURE 1 RESULTS FROM SURVEY - ARE YOU FAMILIAR WITH THE MOBILIZATION AND MUTUAL LEARNING (MML) METHODOLOGY AND WORKSHOPS?

2. The MML methodology has been utilised to produce Research & Innovation in universities only by two HEIs in CATALISI (see figure 2). However, the use of this methodology was specifically related to the context of other H2020 projects, or related to the solution of specific challenges (such as city problems or Social & Health Services, Environment and Pollution, Health, Social Services). Therefore, as for now, none of the CATALISI HEIs has utilised MML for the broader purpose of achieving institutional transformation of their own university.

FIGURE 2 RESULTS FROM SURVEY - DO YOU USE MML METHODOLOGY TO FACILITATE TRANSFORMATIONS AND PRODUCE RESEARCH & INNOVATION IN YOUR HEI?

3. KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND MUTUAL LEARNING APPROACH IN CATALISI

Within CATALISI, knowledge sharing and mutual learning is considered a learning method paramount for the achievement of the overall objective of the project, namely to support institutional change of Higher Education Institutions in the field of Research and Innovation. As seen, this approach represents a step forward to the current state of the art on MML.

Overall, knowledge sharing and mutual learning in CATALISI is aimed at:

- ✓ Concretely **supporting HEIs in their institutional transformations** as detailed in their tailored roadmaps (developed in Task 3.2), providing partners with practical knowledge, concrete examples and inputs to achieve and manage institutional transformation over time, in the areas of intervention they deem necessary. In this framework, knowledge sharing and mutual learning can be considered as an effort to broaden the network of people involved in the areas of intervention of institutional change, identify best practices and common solutions, analysing their enabling conditions and discussing actionable knowledge and potential solutions for the implementation and sustainability of institutional changes. Knowledge sharing and mutual learning will also support implementing partners to collect ideas on their intervention area, explore different options and scenarios, through the **sharing of experiences, best practices and points of views** with other HEIs, relevant quadruple-helix stakeholders and Community of Practice (CoP) experts.
- ✓ Fostering exchange of knowledge between HEIs to **disseminate** the knowledge and know-how achieved on the areas of transformation also to other societal actors. In fact, MML actions allow discussion and cooperation between science and society at different stages of the research and innovation process.

To pursue these aims, specific opportunities will be provided through knowledge-sharing and mutual learning activities:

- Bringing a culture of knowledge-sharing by fostering a **supportive environment** of collaboration, openness, and mutual learning among implementers and stakeholders
- Fostering a sense of **co-creation** among stakeholders and implementers, by engaging them in joint activities, discussions, and knowledge-sharing
- Encouraging **capacity-building** in managing R&I over time
- Helping HEIs to **gain awareness of and formalize** what they actually have learnt from their own experience and disseminate it to other actors
- **Identifying and promote** best practices and examples of successful institutional transformation initiatives in HEIs
- Facilitating a **comparison among the different institutional changes** allowing to generate a more comprehensive and in-depth knowledge of HEIs institutional transformations and outcomes as they emerge from the practice of the partners
- Capitalizing on the experience of other Implementers **creating a common framework** for the process of developing and implementing institutional roadmaps
- Contributing to **increase knowledge** on how to stimulate institutional changes thanks to the experience in CATALISI
- **Validating project results** and ensure that they are aligned with the needs and expectations of stakeholders in the quadruple helix (academia, industry, policy-makers, and civil society).

Such opportunities are also a reflection of the interest expressed by CATALISI partners in the use of MML to achieve institutional transformation, as derived from the survey results, presented in the figure here below.

FIGURE 3 RESULTS FROM SURVEY – OPPORTUNITIES OF MML IN CATALISI

6. Which opportunities would you like to take advantage through MML events?

[More Details](#)

In addition, knowledge exchange and mutual learning established in CATALISI builds upon the exchange of experiences and points of view between **different actors**. Implementers will in fact benefit from the exchange of knowledge and experience of other Implementers (HEIs of the project), from the experience of project Facilitators and external experts, as well as from the expertise of relevant quadruple-helix stakeholders. On one hand, the exchange of knowledge **amongst HEIs (peers)** supports mutual learning on how other implementers have already performed specific institutional changes. On the other hand, Implementers will benefit from the knowledge exchange with **external experts** (such as Community of Practice (CoP) members) and from the involvement of targeted **quadruple-helix stakeholders** in MML activities, which is key to contribute and deliver impactful outcomes (action plans, agreements, collaborations) in the areas of institutional transformations and to enable meaningful exchange between the academia and the outside realm. The mapping of key quadruple-helix stakeholders that are either involved or impacted by CATALISI actions (T1.2) and the mapping of Community of Practice members (from T6.3), will be crucial for this purpose.

In a long-term, mutual learning can be also understood as a general approach to guarantee permanent institutional changes in a way in which an organisation works. This means modifying the norms (mission, procedures, protocol, organisational structures, etc.) but also the social patterns (cognitive, emotional, relational, behavioural, etc.) which are shared by majority of people inside the organisation. In such a context, the involvement of **local actors in each HEI**, including **low, middle and top-level managers**, is key to create the conditions inside a research organisation for mobilising and coordinating all the concerned actors towards R&I. Top level managers (including Deputies, Vice-chancellors university secretaries, Academic registrars) have a strategic role in Universities. Involving them is key to achieve organizational change in universities, by putting pressure on modifying the organizational structures. Middle-management (i.e. Principals, Deans, Directors, Head of department, Deputy, Finance directors), have a Tactical role) whilst Lower management (academic staff and administrative staff) have an operational role (Mande et al., 2015). All these internal categories of actors are key to bring institutional transformation in HEIs, whether from a social (bottom-up) or organizational (top-down) approach.

CATALISI will therefore consider knowledge exchange and mutual learning both as a learning method and a general approach to institutional change encompassing different levels of knowledge exchange. In CATALISI, knowledge exchange and mutual learning is regarded a dynamic and evolving process depending on the different phases of the project and the needs of involved actors.

4. SET UP OF THE KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND MUTUAL LEARNING EVENTS

Knowledge sharing and mutual learning will encompass different learning activities throughout the project duration. In particular, the knowledge exchange and mutual learning process in CATALISI will entail three main components:

- Mobilisation and Mutual learning onsite workshops (T2.3)
- Mutual learning online events (T6.3);
- Exchange of knowledge through Twinning schemes (T2.4).

4.1 MML ONSITE WORKSHOPS

MML onsite Workshops are events where Implementers can exchange experiences and knowledge on their respective intervention areas and transformational pathways. They are organized to connect different HEIs around Europe to share their knowledge, best practices, expertise in their areas of transformation.

During the project, **seven onsite MML workshops**, will be organized, one in each implementer location. All implementers will be involved plus APRE as the task leader, who will be the facilitator in each workshop.

The host Implementers' role is twofold:

- 1) **To deepen and transfer the knowledge** with regards to the respective area of intervention also to the other participants
- 2) To take advantage of the MML workshop to **improve, advance and consolidate the process of institutional transformation** in their own HEI.

In general, the structure of the onsite MML workshops will include:

- A first session devoted to a frontal open exchange on **inspirational examples** that each host implementer will share on the different intervention areas and their ongoing processes of institutional transformation as declined in their roadmap (T3.2). This initial part will provide the opportunity to introduce and discuss the specificities of each selected intervention area, ongoing processes, and successful examples. It will also allow for the contribution of speakers/stakeholders from different parts of the host institution (including **low, middle and top-level managers of HEIs**) and from the **quadruple-helix** (deriving from T1.2 stakeholder mapping), providing potentially unique insights and first-hand experiences.
- A second session for **co-creating new pathways** for the implementations of institutional changes. Implementers will have the opportunity to allow exchange and discussion with the speakers and with the other participants. In this part, co-creation specific methodologies will be adopted (flipcharts, billboard, post-its, interactive digital means etc.).

Depending on the state of implementation of their transformational actions (as defined in T3.2), and the process of institutional transformation each university is at (started/in progress/finalised), this session may aim to:

- Provide implementers with input and solution of problems on their ongoing institutional transformation roadmap, discussing and evaluating (on the basis of WP4 identified evaluation indicators), the transformational roadmaps with local actors and other participants.
- Discuss the achievements, the impacts and the sustainability of the implemented actions.
- Also, this session will support the generation of new knowledge and ideas for all other participating HEIs in the specific area of intervention discussed. This

will provide all other participating HEIs with valuable insights to implement changes in the specific domain also in their own HEI.

- Each workshop will end with an **evaluation exercise** for the collection of immediate feedback by participants.

TABLE 1 - STRUCTURE OF ONSITE MML WORKSHOPS

Implementer (host of the workshop)	Focus of the workshop	Invited speakers	Participants
HEI name	Priority of intervention area for institutional transformation	Relevant stakeholders (HEIs managers and/or external quadruple-helix stakeholders) according to expertise in the topic	All other CATALISI HEIs, internal HEI actors including low, middle and top-level managers, quadruple-helix stakeholders according to interest and experience in the topic

The topics of the workshops will be based on implementers' needs and priorities with regards to the respective area of intervention. The values, concerns, needs and expectations from CATALISI living labs (WP1) as well as the short-term goals as defined in the first version (due in M8) of the transformational pathways (T3.2) will be analysed to identify common and specific requirements, expertise and agenda-setting of each implementer. The aim of the analysis is to optimize the workshops' content and usefulness by focusing only on the selected intervention areas and actions, and by identifying and inviting all stakeholders potentially involved in all aspects of the implementation activities.

A preliminary overview of topics that HEIs considered more relevant to organise MML workshops, can be appreciated from the results of the online survey and displayed in the Figure 4 here below (more than one answer per HEI was possible). A deeper analysis will further derive from D.1.2 and the first version of the D.3.3 due in M8.

FIGURE 4: PRELIMINARY OVERVIEW OF TOPICS CONSIDERED RELEVANT FOR MML ONSITE WORKSHOPS BY CATALISI HEIS

8. Which topics would you consider more relevant for you to organise an onsite MML in your institution?
(preliminary overview)

[More Details](#)

● Research assessment reform	5
● Qualifications and research carr...	4
● Digitisation of HE sector	1
● Researchers' circulation/mobility	6
● Human capital and Lifelong lear...	4
● Gender equality & inclusiveness	0
● Open science/open access	3
● Science education & public eng...	3
● Sustainability in Education (fund...	3
● Sustainability in research	7
● Sustainability in Campus Operat...	3
● Others	0

The host organizer (each HEI) will focus on the detailed plan and preparation work. The agenda of each workshop is established through a consultation process with APRE. APRE will help Implementers setting up the agenda and in defining the most appropriate formats for the workshops, based on the Implementers' inputs. During the sessions, APRE will be the moderator.

During the preparatory phase (M9-M12), APRE will support Implementing partners with the organisation of MML events ensuring the definition of the following aspects and agenda-setting, based on the methodological guidelines and work plan as outlined in Section 5:

- ✓ Decision on topic / drafting of the programme
- ✓ List with invitees and participants
- ✓ Recruitment of facilitators & speakers
- ✓ Seeking venue
- ✓ Book date / venue
- ✓ Specify workshop set-up
- ✓ Send invitations
- ✓ Send reminder to invitees with programme
- ✓ Print final guide and formats
- ✓ Organise equipment
- ✓ Organise food, drinks
- ✓ Organise the dissemination of the workshop

4.2 MUTUAL LEARNING ONLINE EVENTS

MML online events will be organized by APRE to support CATALISI implementers in their roadmaps towards institutional transformation through the promotion of **best practices, knowledge exchange and inspirational examples with experts of the CATALISI Community of Practice (CoP)** members, as defined in WP6 (T6.3).

A Community of Practice is a group of people who share a common interest, profession, or goal and regularly engage in collaborative learning and knowledge sharing. The Community

of Practice (CoP) can play a crucial role in achieving the aim to support institutional transformation in higher education institutions (HEIs) by bringing together a group of experts and experienced professionals who provide advice and guidance on methodologies, knowledge, resources, infrastructures, and tools.

The CoP can provide a platform for knowledge sharing, collaboration, and innovation, and can support the project activities by providing their expertise, methods, stories, cases, and studies/publications. In this way, the CoP can contribute to the development of a body of knowledge and best practices that can inform and guide the project activities, and can also create examples that allow people to learn by doing.

In addition, the CoP can help to engage a range of stakeholders from the quadruple helix, including industry partners, policy-makers, and civil society organizations, who can provide support for co-creative events in terms of promotion of collaboration, innovation, and knowledge transfer.

The CoP can thus play a critical role in facilitating the development and dissemination of knowledge and tools related to institutional transformation in HEIs, as well as in creating a sustainable network of individuals and organizations committed to this goal.

To summarise, the CoP can provide:

- ✓ Expertise and knowledge sharing: Members of the CoP can engage in joint activities, discussions, and share experiences.
- ✓ Collaboration and innovation: The CoP can provide a platform for collaboration and innovation, where members can work together to develop new ideas, approaches, and solutions related to institutional transformation in HEIs. This can help to generate new insights, practices, and tools that can inform and guide the project activities and can also create opportunities for cross-fertilization of ideas and experiences.
- ✓ Support for co-creative events: The CoP can provide support for co-creative events in terms of promotion of collaboration, innovation, and knowledge transfer.

Minimum two MML online events with CoP members will be planned during the CATALISI implementation period and will last around 2 hours focusing on transversal topics common to and of interest to many implementing partners. Overall, MML online events aim to monitor, fine-tune the activities, extract the actionable knowledge and deliver recommendations for CATALISI future activities.

CATALISI CoP members (national and European level) will be invited to participate in these workshops, providing inspirational examples, promoting best practices and advising the implementers on innovative approaches and potential challenges related to the implementation of institutional change in Higher Education Institutions.

Topics of the online MML will derive from Implementers' needs which are constantly mapped and collected throughout the project. Preliminary topics of the MML online events include:

- Institutional transformation of HEIs for R&I: definition, advantages, potential barriers, experiences, sustainability and management of transformations.
- Creation of market-place opportunities: (i.e., identification of funding schemes, collaborations and alliances, opportunities for researchers to commercialise their research results).
- Mapping needs and providing innovative education design methods and approaches on common HEIs priority interests (i.e. sustainability in research; researchers' mobility & circulation; researcher assessment reform).
-

4.3 TWINNING SCHEMES

The Twinning scheme service aims at creating a twinning mechanism to facilitate the transfer and implementation of innovative practices amongst HEIs around Europe. The scope is to achieve tangible operational results through **peer-to-peer activities** and best practices exchange. In fact, through the Twinning schemes, Implementers will secure knowledge sharing and experience how other implementers (peers) have already performed institutional changes.

Twinning between Less-Experienced and Experienced HEIs: The exchange will happen based on a two-sided framework dependent on the specific topic related to the intervention area of each HEI. A preliminary phase (M7-M10) will aim to achieve a **matchmaking** between more experienced and less experienced HEIs in specific topic of interventions.

During the project, the Twinning exchange will be organised in the following way:

- **All HEI will visit at least three other implementer organisations.** The analysis deriving from the needs assessment (WP1) will allow to match HEIs needs, interests and expertise amongst Implementers. This way, those HEIs which hold more knowledge about a specific topic will be able to transfer it to those HEIs who need it. On the basis of the analysis of WP1 we will define groups of HEIs interested in the same topics in order to define a calendar.
- At least **three HEIs will be hosting** the Twinning schemes. In fact, it is not mandatory that all universities are Experienced-hosting universities. When universities have few expertise in their teams related to certain topics of interest, they will be visiting other HEIs which have more expertise on those topics of interest, and will not be hosting any Twinning exchange on those matters.
- Twinning exchanges should last around two working days and comprise 'mentoring' sessions at the hosting HEI.
- **At least 2 executive staff² per university** will be involved in the Twinning schemes allowing institutional transformations, by using their position and role to make pressures on social and organizational changes. This means that between 2 and 6 executive members will visit the three HEIs. It is recommended to select different people according to the topic of interest and expertise or specific role in the university, so to bring effective value to the training exchange. Also, attention to gender balance of the participants is important.
- Each year specific **topics** are chosen to be reinforced through exchanges that are carried out in presence. These topics will be related to the **domains of institutional transformation** (Year 1: Human Capital; Year 2: Research Modus Operandi; Year 3: Finance). When possible, Twinning schemes will be organised after each of the webinars (T2.1). This way, implementers will have the opportunity to deepen, at a practical level, the theoretical knowledge achieved throughout the webinars on the specific topic/intervention area and to visit the Implementing partner which has expertise and knowledge about the defined topic.
- APRE, as task leader, will support the preparation of the **agenda** prior to the visit, including selection of participants and training sessions/activities, making sure that the exchange is as fruitful as possible for both host and visiting HEI. To this end, a careful planning phase will take place between M7-M10 so to match interests and expertise and give HEIs time to organise internal calendars.
- **An event reporting template** will (see Annex B) help define the agenda and evaluate the outcomes of the Twinning scheme and will feed the deliverable due on December 2025 (D.2.3 "Twinning scheme report").

² Executive staff is intended as CATALISI Core team and extended team, which will derive from the mapping of key internal stakeholders (stakeholder mapping from T1.2).

TABLE 2 TWINNING METHODOLOGY IN CATALISI³

Topic (Domain of intervention)	Experienced HEI (host trainer)	Names and Roles	HEI name and country
Year 1: Human Capital	Experienced HEIs (host trainer)		
	Less experienced HEIs (visiting HEI trainees)		
Year 2: Research Modus Operandi	Experienced HEIs (host trainer)		
	Less experienced HEIs (visiting HEI trainees)		
Year 3: Finance	Experienced HEIs (host trainer)		
	Less experienced HEIs (visiting HEI trainees)		

5. CAPITALISATION OF KNOWLEDGE AND KNOW-HOW

The three components of the Mutual Learning Plan are overall thought to create a mutual learning environment which allows implementing partners to develop their transformational roadmaps through peer-to-peer activities and best practices exchange and to increase their skills and capacities in managing R&I over time.

To support this process, APRE will facilitate a capitalisation of knowledge and know-how generated through the activities connected with mutual learning, including those which are of informal nature, on the one hand, by ensuring a reporting of the Mutual Learning Workshops and the Mutual Learning Online events (Deliverable 2.2 on 30 June 25) and, on the other hand, interacting with implementing partners, on a periodical basis, in order to help them turning their experience into new skills and lessons learned.

6. SHAPE OF THE MML EVENTS

This section provides Implementers with **practical guidelines and a methodology to follow** for the preparation of onsite MML workshops. Their quality and impact is dependent on a relevant and clear outcome, output, and topic. Moreover, the ability to attract participants who can contribute and who have capacity for action is crucial.

³ Names of participants taking part of the Twinning schemes, their role in the university and name of CATALISI HEI will be defined after a careful analysis deriving from WP1 (D.1.2) and WP3 (First version of D.3.3) due in M8.

6.1 DEFINE THE OUTPUT/OUTCOME

In the preparation for an MML event, it is important to define the intended output and outcome, otherwise it is challenging to have a focused and meaningful dialogue that actually sets change in motion. Outputs are defined as results achieved immediately after the event (e.g. documents, reports, etc.), while outcomes are defined as longer-term results, such as follow-up activities. Both will be indicated in the template of the event's report, which can also be used as a guideline in the design phase (see APPENDIX A – DRAFT MML EVENT REPORT).

The clear definition of the outputs and the expected outcome of each event is essential for the next steps of the event preparation, including the definition of the guiding questions and the definition of the participants who needs to be involved in the activities.

The Agenda should include:

1. the abstract of the event and the expected results (e.g. output and outcomes);
2. the subscription form: this is very important and must include at least these field:
 - a. Name
 - b. Surname
 - c. Email
 - d. Organization
 - e. Country
3. The actual agenda for the day with the speakers and topic.

The registration form should include the field regarding the Consent form, in accordance with the principles laid out by GDPR (article 6.1.a and 6.1.f).

6.2 IDENTIFY THE TOPIC

In the preparation for an MML workshop, it is important to formulate a clear topic to define the problem that requires further understanding and to formulate potential solutions with the contribution of all event participants.

CATALISI works on the complex matter of Institutional Changes of HEIs in different domains and intervention areas. Such complex matter comprises several areas of discussion and could be tackled with a broader approach or with a more target approach, through the involvement of specific stakeholders to discuss specific progress and to ensure the achievement of sustainable Institutional Changes.

- To identify the topic of MML onsite workshops, CATALISI partners should define the **intervention area** which is more relevant to share and to have inputs/feedback from the invited participants and stakeholders, and which could enable them to achieve institutional changes in the long-run.
- In case Implementers give priority to more than one intervention area, it is recommended to select only one of these topics, in order to share and receive more targeted input and feedback.

Moreover, in the case of co-creation activities during MML workshops, Implementers are encouraged to keep a balance between keeping the topic broad enough to benefit from the contribution of different actors, and at the same time narrow enough to ensure that the interaction leads to concrete outputs (e.g. actions to include in the Roadmaps). Especially in the case of these events, as participants are attending on a voluntary basis, it is crucial that the topic is relevant for them and that they see the importance of their contribution to the project's activities in a friendly and positive environment.

6.3 IDENTIFY STAKEHOLDERS AND SELECT PARTICIPANTS

Depending on the overall aim of the event organized, the expected outputs and outcomes, and the local context, the organizing HEI will decide who to invite to the MML event to ensure the most productive environment. It is also important to keep in mind an appropriate number of participants. A large number of participants may not always be the right choice, especially for events where concrete actions have to be defined.

With this in mind, for each onsite MML workshop organized, the following actors are highly encouraged to participate:

- **Different hierarchical levels inside the organization (low, middle and top-managers)** should be involved since the process of knowledge sharing is intended to be multilevel within institutions. Involving **top-level managers** in MML workshops as speakers or participants is key to achieve organizational change in universities, by putting pressure on modifying the organizational structures (norms, procedures and protocols). To mitigate the risk of top-level managers not attending MML workshops, all HEIs implementers have signed a commitment letter prior the access to the preparation of CATALISI proposal and these letters were signed by high-level managers committing the organization in the transformation. However, in cases in which involving top-level managers may represent a crucial challenge for HEIs, it will be considered to dedicate one-hour of discussion with top level managers and leaders to present the project, its aims achievements and expectations as a consortium.
- For each of the onsite Mutual Learning workshops, Implementers should also invite **participants beyond the project team** already involved in the project (i.e. **core and extended team**). In fact, collaboration between different HEI groups and departments, involving local actors in the HEI is deemed necessary i.e. researchers, support staff, governance members within each partner's organization, in accordance to the topic of interest which is discussed⁴.
- **External actors from the quadruple-helix** should participate to enable meaningful and useful exchange between the academia and outside realm. At the same time, it is important to keep a balanced representation across the participants (e.g. types of quadruple helix actors, gender, etc.), unless the specific topic of the event is clearly of more interest to a specific category of stakeholders. In fact, if in some areas of intervention the involvement of specific external actors may be less crucial.
- For both online and onsite events, it is important to invite **experts for keynote speeches**. They can bring their expertise to the discussion as a showcase of success cases and stories, role models, the point of view of a High-Level Institution.

In reaching out to participants, it is recommended to consider the best way to approach them and to provide them, in due time, with all the relevant information about their expected contribution and benefits they can gain from the event. An adequate preparation of the participants is considered one of the success factors of the Knowledge sharing and Mutual Learning events.

⁴ To map key stakeholders a reflection tool may be useful. According to this methodology, stakeholders involved in the projects' activities are the core team with a co-managing role, and the extended team with a co-producing role (cf. Vilarchao et al., 2022 <https://zenodo.org/record/7022933#.Yy2R1ezMLgE>). However, internal CATALISI members are heterogeneous: some teams already include people working in Grant Offices, whilst others are composed of researchers. This requires effort to involve and engage key internal actors.

6.4 DEFINE THE ACTIVITIES

Once the outputs, outcomes, topic and participants have been defined, it is time to prepare the activities that will be carried out during the MML workshop. The partner responsible for organizing the event is encouraged to circulate among the CATALISI partners a short **concept note** of the event with clear definitions of expected outputs and outcomes, topic and participants, for example by using the format of the reporting template (see APPENDIX A – DRAFT MML EVENT REPORT).

Next step is to **select a date and time** for the event that takes into account university's internal agenda, the availability of participants and the preparation time needed. This includes the choice of an appropriate length for the event, which must ensure the achievement of the event's objectives and at the same time take into account the commitment required, especially from stakeholders external to the project's activities. Considering university's internal agenda and the time needed to secure external participants' availability, it is therefore essential for HEIs to plan out the most appropriate timing of the workshop in advance and to secure the date as early as possible.

Finally, it is important to choose a proper location. In the case of face-to-face events, one must take into consideration the space necessary for the chosen activities.

6.5 EVALUATION OF MMLS

At the end of each workshop, an "evaluation of the workshops" could be used for the impact assessment of the project, specifically about the usefulness and set-up of the workshops. In practice, the exercise can consist in rating some aspects of the workshop and answering questions, including open questions such as:

- What are the most important takeaways from the workshop?
- What are the highlights of the workshop?
- What could be improved for the next workshop?

The report (see APPENDIX A – DRAFT MML EVENT REPORT), includes an assessment of the outputs of the events, expected outcomes and an evaluation with a focus on lessons learnt (both in terms of success factors and difficulties encountered).

6.6 MML FORMATS AND TECHNIQUES

MML events follow a structure in which plenary and subgroup interaction alternate. The workshop usually starts with a plenary kick-off, followed by subgroups and closed again in a plenary set-up. They are based on different formats, including simulations, brainstorming sessions, experience exchanges and guided discussions.

Implementing partner countries can choose to adjust or even use different MML techniques if they believe that this is needed to achieve the desirable dialogue and outcome. Table 2 illustrates several techniques for each of the MML workshops.

TABLE 3: LIST OF TECHNIQUES FOR MML WORKSHOPS

Techniques for MML Workshops	Description
Speed Dating	Speed dating is also used as an 'icebreaker' or team building exercise as it generates multiple brief one-one interactions. For the MML workshop speed dating can also be used to generate meaningful dialogue in duos.
Open Space	Designed to allow a group to self-organize in the exploration of a relevant topic of concern. The group discusses the shared question in break-out sessions with a self-organized agenda. Topics come to the fore suggested by participants who have enough expertise and responsibility to explore them
Digital audience response	An option is to use audience response systems during the plenary part to realize interaction between the presenter and his or her (larger) audience.
Brainstorming (with idea mapping)	Brainstorming is a creative group technique in which people collectively generate a list of ideas and solutions around a specific topic of interest or problem in a spontaneous way. In the plenary introduction the problem owner already gave a short presentation of the question at hand. During a brainstorming people are invited to think more freely and to voice as many ideas as they have.
Design thinking	Design thinking helps a group of people from a shared understanding of a problem to a way to prototype and test solutions. The five known steps are (1) Empathize, (2) Define, (3) Ideate, (4) Prototype, (5) Test.
Pitches	Pitches are a short presentation of five minutes to create space to discuss multiple topics in a limited time. Examples are the perspectives of each helix group actor with the institutional transformation. Having short presentations forces presenters to share only the essential elements to make a point. The general idea is that the audience will remain more focused during the talks. The formats differ greatly between conferences. Some may encourage the use of slides, some have specific set-ups.
World Cafè	Flexible and simple format for hosting large group dialogues. Participants explore the same question in multiple, parallel conversations, and then people rotate to different tables (or breakout rooms) to exchange ideas. Towards the end, the group often takes time to make common meaning of the patterns they have discussed. It is useful to maximize dialogue and engagement, brainstorm in small clusters and then transfer the information gathered to other groups. A simple structure of a World café could be: a. Preparation of the room, or access to the virtual room: a friendly environment with tables, flipcharts and sticky notes (for the virtual version, Miro can be used); b. Welcome and introduction by the facilitator;

	c. First round of conversation, small groups: each group focuses on a single question/topic (suggested time: 20 minutes); d. Second round of conversation, plenary group: to share insights or other results from small groups with the rest of the participants.

APRE, as leader and facilitator of the MML activities, can bring to CATALISI activities several online useful tools that can be used in such occasions:

- Miro: a collaborative whiteboard platform that enables participants to work together, from brainstorming with digital sticky notes to planning and managing agile workflows;
- Slido: a question and answers and polling platform for online, onsite or hybrid events;
- Mentimeter: an online tool to share polls and reach feedback in an interactive way.

7. SCHEDULE OF THE KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND MUTUAL LEARNING EVENTS

The Knowledge Sharing and Mutual Learning Plan will develop throughout the CATALISI project. Therefore, its contents will evolve together with the evolution of the project. Functioning as a support structure for facilitating the implementation of transformational pathways (T3.2), such contents will largely depend on the demands and needs expressed by the implementing partners over time. However, a general framework for the different phases of the project can be defined (see the tables below). It is to remind that Task 2.3 related to onsite MML workshops, starts in June 2023 (M6 of the project) and ends in June 2025 (M30 of the project), whilst Task 2.4, related to Twinning schemes, starts in June 2023 (M6 of the project) and ends in December 2025 (M36 of the project).

7.1 TIMELINE OF MML WORKSHOPS

Since the first version of the transformational pathways (T3.2) and the first needs assessment deriving from Acting Living labs (D1.1) will be due in M8 (August 2023), a careful preparation of the MML workshops, which is tailored on Implementers' needs, expertise and agenda setting, will take place soon afterwards, between M9-M12.

The MML onsite workshops will take place **every two months**, one in each implementing partner country and will take place **not before M13 (January 2024)**, in order to make the workshops as efficient as possible for the Implementing partners based on the development of their action plan (as defined in T.3.2). The scheduling of the onsite workshops will in fact depend on the state of the action plan development in each HEIs (as defined in their transformational roadmaps) as well as internal HEIs' agenda. APRE will be flexible to accommodate to HEIs' calendar in order to make the MML workshops as fruitful as possible and to ensure a well-represented participation of key stakeholders to be involved.

TABLE 4 TENTATIVE TIMELINE FOR ONSITE MML WORKSHOPS

Date	Description of activity	Location
M9 - M12 (Sep – Dec 2023)	Preparation phase of MML workshops materials and scheduling workshops	Desk analysis and Online
M13 (January 2024)	1 st MML workshop in implementing partner country	(TBD)
M15 (March 2024)	2 nd MML workshop in implementing partner country	(TBD)
M17 (May 2024)	3 rd workshop in implementing partner country	(TBD)
M19 (July 2024)	4 th workshop in implementing partner country	(TBD)
M21 (Sept 2024)	5 th workshop in implementing partner country	(TBD)
M23 (Nov 2024)	6 th workshop in implementing partner country	(TBD)
M25 (Jan 2025)	7 th workshop in implementing partner country	(TBD)

TABLE 5 TENTATIVE TIMELINE FOR MML ONLINE EVENTS

Date	Topic	Speakers invited	Location
M10 (October 2023)	Institutional Transformation of HEIs	CoP members, external experts	Online
M26 (February 2025)	TBD	CoP members, external experts	Online

7.2 TIMELINE OF TWINNING SCHEMES

The Twinning Schemes will take place in yearly cycles based on the Implementers' roadmap (T3.2) and specific areas of interventions and priorities (deriving from WP1), matched with other HEIs expertise who will be hosting the exchange. On the basis of the analysis deriving from WP1 and T3.2 (first version of transformational roadmaps) we will define groups of HEIs interested in the same topics in order to define a calendar.

A preliminary phase (M7-M10) will aim to achieve a matchmaking between more experienced and less experienced HEIs based on the outcomes of WP1.

Based on Implementers' calendar and expressed preferences (collected during Consortium Meeting at M6), the first Twinning exchanges will take place from November 2023 (M11).

TABLE 6 TENTATIVE TIMELINE FOR TWINNING SCHEMES

Date	Topics (based on HEIs priority areas of intervention as defined in WP1)	HEIs hosting (experienced)	Visiting HEIs names (less experienced)
(Year 1) Nov - Dec 2023	Domain 1	Host HEIs experienced on the topics (as emerged from WP1)	# HEIs
(Year 2) Jan - Dec 2024	Domain 2	Host HEIs experienced on the topics (as emerged from WP1)	# HEIs
(Year 3) Jan - Nov 2025	Domain 3	Host HEIs experienced on the topics (as emerged from WP1)	# HEIs

8. CONCLUSION

This document aims at transferring methodological guidelines to CATALISI partners for the implementation of activities related to Knowledge Sharing and Mobilisation of Mutual learning. Nevertheless, it could be the starting point for everyone interested in the implementation of activities which involve knowledge transfer and mutual learning, specifically related to institutional transformation of universities or other institutions.

This document will be directly tested by the consortium in the upcoming events, with a view to make the most out of the in-the-field feedback and operational experience, aiming at improving the way to provide future support to participative research and knowledge sharing mutual learning events.

9. REFERENCES

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APPENDIX A – DRAFT MML EVENT REPORT

Event name:

Date:

Name of the organization in charge of the event:

General Information:

Venue	
Length	
Date	
Organizer	
Total number of participants	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of the event.

List of Participants

Please include the list of participants

Name	Organisation	Role

Overall Event assessment

Overall, how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please, briefly justify your answer.

Event Description

Please briefly describe the event including:

Aim of event	
Output(s)	
Expected outcome(s)	
Topic	

<p>Type of participants (e.g. Academia, Research Funding Organizations, Policy-Makers, Civil Society, Business, CS initiatives, others to specify)</p>	
<p>Activities performed</p>	

APPENDIX B – DRAFT TWINNING REPORT

Twinning Group:

Twinning Group Host:

Twinning Dates:

Twinning Group TRAINEES:

	Name	Organisation name and country
Assisting Trainer		
Trainees		

Overall Event assessment

1. What would you consider as the most helpful feature offered by you during this Twinning?
2. What would you consider as (any) difficulties?
3. What were the highlights and most important achievements/ activities during this Twinning? (Host only)
4. What improvements and suggestions (if any) would you make for future twinning?
5. Quality and appropriateness of Programme / Agenda
6. Trainees contribution to Programme / Agenda, interaction with Assisting Trainer, Trainees active participation